

Brazil in Modern architectural handbooks

«The chain links are reciprocally sent back to each other and the whole chain is sustained in emptiness. (...) The dog believes to bite a bone, when, in reality, it is biting its own tail».
Ginzburg, Apud Tafuri (1984)

Introduction

The inclusion of modern Brazilian architecture in the so-called *architectural handbooks* both indicates the recognition and consolidation of this movement and conforms to the internationally disseminated historiographical image on the theme. The first references to Brazilian architecture can be found in Bruno Zevi's first edition of *Storia dell'Architettura Moderna* (1950), Gillo Dorfles' first edition of *L'Architettura Moderna* (1956), and Pevsner's sixth edition of *An Outline of European Architecture* (1957). Although brief, references to Warchavchik's work can also be found in Sartoris' 1931 handbook, *Gli elementi dell'Architettura Funzionale*.

Brasília, in spite of the profuse criticism it provoked, is the fact that affirms the success of this production, and exactly after its construction, most modern architecture history handbooks –except for Sartoris' (1931), Zevi's (1950), Dorfles' (1956) and Pevsner's (1957)– start referring to this peripheral movement.

Besides being included in the above mentioned works, Brazil appears in the first editions of both Hitchcock's *Architecture, nineteenth and twentieth centuries* (1958) as well as Benévolo's *Storia dell'Architettura Moderna* (1960), and, indirectly, in the foreword to the 1963 edition of Giedion's *Space, Time and Architecture* (1941). Later on, it also appears in Tafuri's (*Architettura Contemporanea*, 1976) and Frampton's (*Modern Architecture: a critical his-*

tory, 1980) handbooks. The trajectory of modern architectural production presented by Giedion in *A Decade of Contemporary Architecture* (1951) and the articles, «Architettura Moderna in Brasile», published by Argan in the magazine *Comunità* (1954), and «Modern architecture and the historian or the return of historicism», written by Pevsner for *RIBA Journal* (1961), also deserve attention.

Making use of the historiographical interpretation model proposed by Scalvini (1984) in *L'Immagine Storiografica dell'Architettura Contemporanea da Platón a Giedion* –an adaptation to historical texts of the interpretative model of architectural work formulated by Bonta (1977) in *Sistemas de Significación en arquitectura: un estudio de la arquitectura y su interpretación*–, we can identify, in the handbooks, from a retrospective view, three moments of the process of construction of a canonical version of modern Brazilian architecture history: pre-canonical answers, emergency of a canonical interpretation and reinterpretations.

Zevi (1950), Giedion (1951), Dorfles (1956) and Pevsner (1957) represent pre-canonical answers – still little developed visions that constitute the first attempts at classifying this architecture, when its paradigmatic examples had not been chosen yet.

Hitchcock (1958) and Benévolo (1960) as well as Pevsner (1961) and Giedion (1963) represent the emergence of a canonical version, based on which the participation of Brazilian architectural production in the modern movement is spread out and recognised. As such, they set what appears to be essential to them –that is, three or four protagonists as well as a restricted and punctual image of the country's production– and discard all nuances.

The fully revised edition of Zevi's handbook (1973), which dedicates more room to Brazilian architecture –classified as neoexpressionist– and ought to represent a reinterpretation, repeats the ideas formulated in some articles written for *Cronache di Architettura*, in the fifties. Tafuri (1976) adds little to Zevi's analysis and, following another line, Frampton (1980) presents no novelty, except for his emphasis on critical regionalism and the argument on the relationship between architecture and place, a reference to works previous to the sixties.

By getting away from the prevalent narrative model and by presenting new analytical methods, Argan (1971) actually proposes a reinterpretation of modern architecture. In 1954, however, the historian who recognised, in *Architettura Moderna in Brasile*, Brazilian architecture as a movement and not a mere exception, does not mention the theme in his handbook, *L'Arte Moderna*, published in 1971.

Based on these presuppositions, the objective of this investigation is to understand how –that is, with

which shades, from which angles and with which instruments— historians' handbooks on modern architecture contribute to the constitution and consolidation of an image of modern Brazilian architecture.

The pre-canonical answers

In the process of constitution of a canonical version, the modern architecture handbooks written at the beginning of the fifties—based mainly on international architecture magazines (1, 2, 3) (*L'Architecture d'Aujourd'hui*, *Architectural Review* and *Architectural Forum*, among others) and characterised as pre-canonical answers— treat Brazilian production as something new as well as remarkable, and generally include a small sample of it, chosen with certain investigative curiosity. As a result, their evaluations turn out to be temporary and full of questions.

The authors of the first handbooks, among other statements, constantly relate Brazilian architecture to the *lecorbusieran* production: by classifying it as part of the so called *third generation*, that coincides with the «crisis of rationalism» formulated by Zevi (1950); by identifying it with the «insurrection against reason» pointed out by Pevsner (1961); or by relating it to the «regionalisms» detected by Dorfles (1956).

Similarly, Zevi (1950) refers to the theme of simplicity, which is directly linked to Le Corbusier, although, in this case, he understands that Brazilian architecture gets away from «abstraction» and comes close to «mechanical, cryptographic» simplicity and «inventive poverty».

The question of formalism is also linked to the official character of such architecture, expressed in the «search for monumentality», according to Zevi (1954); in the «structural acrobatics», as stated by Pevsner (1957); and in the «stylistic excess», for Dorfles (1956). Although recognised as a distinct architectural approach, which shows to have some quality and some formal inventiveness, there is relative distrust as to the future of that production, which, in their eyes, privileges the project's plastic qualities — something almost inadmissible for the spirit of the time.

The examples of Brazilian modern architecture that the first handbooks point out are still few, but varied, while the repertoires presented by Argan, in *Architettura Moderna in Brasile* (1954), and by Giedion, in *A Decade of Contemporary Architecture* (1951) are more comprehensive, mainly for the differentiated character of these texts. The building of the Ministério da Educação is the only work both authors mention, and as to Reidy, Niemeyer and the brothers Roberto, distinct works of each appear. Giedion also mentions other architects, whose works, though equally known, are not considered as references in the paradigmatic image that identifies Brazilian architecture: Levi, Moreira,

Warchavchik, Vital Brazil, Mindlin and Afílio Correia Lima (4). Less recognised yet are the architects who appear in Argan's article: Lina Bo (5, 6), Bologna, Kneese de Melo and Jorge Ferreira.

The emergence of a canonical version

In subsequent handbooks published at the end of the fifties, whose texts point out to the emergence of a canonical version, Brazilian architecture is no longer seen as a novelty and begins to become a paradigm. The samples included are more comprehensive, though the examples are more specific and relate to the official production of Rio de Janeiro's architects, frequently limited to and confused with Oscar Niemeyer's work.

Benévolo and Hitchcock, two of the authors who mention Brazil in that period, are the ones who offer a more varied sample of the country's production. Of course, as compared to the subsequent reduction of examples detected in the handbooks published after the sixties, that initial variety was determined not just by the fact that no position in regard to Brazilian architecture had yet been established: what was then regarded as a handbook — i.e., a work with the largest possible number of information as well as a position close to *neutrality* — and the prestige Brazilian modern architecture enjoyed also had influence on that kind of record.

Nice, tolerant or depreciative, most opinions converge to a single protagonist — Oscar Niemeyer (7) — and, sometimes, to his intellectual mentor, Lúcio Costa. Nearly always, there are references to Reidy's architecture (8), mainly to his correct ethical position, and to Burle-Marx's new vision of landscape, too. The emergent historical version on Brazilian architecture basically privileges three or four architects and half a dozen images, unlike the vast material offered in the period's magazines.

The brothers Roberto and Rino Levi (9), quite well known in international architecture magazines, are practically forgotten. Some handbooks, on tracing a historical panorama, mention them, but go no further. Warchavchik (10) is eventually included, too, but always as a historical reference, not as a paradigm.

Also in obscurity remain those who are in the periphery, as, for example: Luís Nunes (11, 12), who works in Pernambuco; the architects from São Paulo, such as Flávio de Carvalho and Artigas (13, 14); the foreign resident architects in São Paulo; and the authors of social housing projects, so very much called for, but rarely the object of historians' attention.

The Ministério da Educação (15) building, Pampulha's chapel (16) and Pedregulho social housing complex (17) are the images, which are spread out in handbooks as examples of the architecture produced in the first half of the century. The Ministério

da Educação is that history's fundamental landmark, and there, the lecorbusieran influence can only be compared to the Portuguese colonial constructive tradition. Pampulha is the work that definitively reveals Niemeyer's inventiveness, for the Ministério da Educação and the New York's Brazilian Pavilion (18) were a result of teamwork. As to Pedregulho, it is the kind of popular housing complex so very much called for by the foreign critics of Brazilian architecture.

The lecorbusieran influence on the country's architecture continues to be identified in the handbooks written after 1960, which consolidate a historiographical version, but now view Brazilian production as something more than a mere climatic adaptation (19, 20, 21) of the French master's fundamentals.

The solar control mechanisms are its more outstanding characteristics and send back both to Le Corbusier and to the Moorish architecture filtered by the Portuguese constructive colonial tradition. These mechanisms are to be developed by Brazilians until they transcend their immediate function and turn into elements of the building's formal definition (22, 23, 24). Historians will see this characteristic either as a virtue or as a defect, a fact that can be observed in the debate about the formalism of that production.

At that moment of diffusion, when the forms of expression proliferate, Hitchcock (1958) — who is interested in researching the manifestations that «move the centre of events away from Europe» — calls attention to individual houses that reveal an eminently American open architecture (25, 26, 27) and also identifies distinctive architectural manifestations in Reidy, Niemeyer, Moreira and the brothers Roberto; similarly, Giedion (1963) sees in the diversity of what he called «polyphonic architecture» a promising future.

The theme of simplicity still persists. For Benévolo (1960) and Giedion (1963), differently from Zevi (1950), it transforms complex programs into simple design, it comes close to sculpture and sends back to an elementary architecture, whose works allow easy reading and can be perceived as a whole; what surprises there is the relationship between the freedom of formal invention and the space in which it is applied.

Negatively evaluated in the first texts, the formalism is recovered by Benévolo (1960), who justifies it as a need for a young country attempting to display a modern character in its architecture. In that search, functional resources turn into aesthetic elements (Hitchcock, 1958), in which there is plenty of plastic boldness, and the generosity of the drawing stands out (Giedion, 1963).

Brasília is obviously the recurrent theme in the handbooks written after the sixties. It constitutes the plan that integrally accomplishes the fundamentals of

modern urbanism (28, 29, 30, 31), spread by Le Corbusier, mainly after the 1933 CIAM, with the Athens Charter. It is also there that Costa appears as the author of the plan, and Niemeyer, as the author of the government palaces, built with the freedom and independence that the country's president, Juscelino Kubitschek, had granted him.

Kubitschek, together with Capanema, embodies the government's support that gives an official character to Brazil's modern architecture. Both represent the authority that Le Corbusier asked for and that allows its development. In the handbooks, that official character would explain some characteristics of that architecture, as, for instance, its formalism, which stands out mainly in Bill and Rogers' argument in *Architectural Review* and *Casabella* (32, 33).

What actually seems to bother historians, however, is the supposed lack of social housing proposals — the program that best characterised the concerns of the Modern Movement. The implicit question was: how can an underdeveloped country of such dimensions, with a high index of growth and such significant architectural production, be so poor in terms of experiences of that kind? The question also applied to the lack of urban experiences: how can a country whose architecture shows to be modern not be so in terms of urban planning? These equally complex correlate subjects are superficially discussed and, to a certain extent, taken into consideration apart from the country's specific economical and political conditions, according to the current concept of autonomous planning of the forties and fifties.

Reinterpretations

After the construction of Brasília and the military coup, the handbooks — that should constitute revisions of that history — repeat previously affirmed plots, restrict examples and are radically critical in relation to Brazil, but cannot be seen as reinterpretations.

In the last group of historians considered here, just Frampton (1980) seems to be actually interested in Brazilian architecture. Tafuri (1976), following Zevi, refers to Niemeyer's architecture as «pure scenery», a fastidious repetition of an architectural formula. Reidy — whose work, Tafuri admits, stands off that formalist model — does not get the historian's attention either, for he has no interest in what he calls the «architecture of bureaucracy». Argan (1971), who had presented one of the soundest evaluations of Brazilian production in 1954, does not include it in *L'Arte Moderna*.

Frampton (1980), frankly interested in the theme, once again reaffirms the importance of Le Corbusier in the renewal of Brazilian architecture; he is one of the few historians who unconditionally sanctions the idea concerning the Brazilian authorship of the

Ministério da Educação; there, he believes to find «a highly sensitive native expression, whose exuberant plasticity recalls to mind the Brazilian Baroque of the XVIII century», and thus retakes the theme Dorfles (1956) had set forth. Frampton also goes back to Max Bill and Zevi's ideas related to the «decadent formalism, useless and characteristically ornamental», that they believe to have seen in Niemeyer's Industry Palace. However, the formulation that gets closer to the reinterpretations of the seventies is the one that identifies, to a certain extent, the Museum of Modern Art of Caracas' inverted pyramid (34) and Brasília's public buildings with the neoclassical tradition.

Concluding

The historians' criticism on Brazilian architecture in the handbooks is coincidental in some points: the texts refer to the same period, the same characters and the same works. This would be understandable if Brazil's modern architectural production were seen as restricted, episodic and punctual, an opinion that neither historians themselves nor the several authors who discussed the theme in specialised magazines have.

If the first manuals significantly contributed to include Brazilian production in the history of modern architecture, the last ones did not add much to this knowledge. The ignorance regarding the country's architecture and geography, which is evident in description mistakes and interpretation misunderstandings, reveal little interest of historians in facing a cultural and intellectual distance, difficult but not impossible to overcome.

As far as this theme is concerned, Rogers (1954), optimistic, believing it possible to understand or, at least, try to understand the artistic manifestations of cultures different from his, thinks it is also possible to make an evaluation of the Brazilian experience, independently from his personal preferences — «surely different from Brazil's architecture and often violently in contrast to it».

Petrina (1991), more radical, criticises the historians who do not move forward in the analysis of Brazilian architecture; in his opinion, this so happens because they have no experience as regards the American space — something considered to be necessary for the development of the subject —, a theme Hitchcock (1958) has dealt with, but dropped:

«... the theme has not been sufficiently analysed, but perhaps, there lie the hidden reasons for the visceral repulsion that such architecture produces in those who, like Bruno Zevi and Max Bill, stuck to the only modernity model they tolerate —the European Rationalism—, attributing, implicit or explicitly, to the modern monumental an academic,

if not frankly reactionary or authoritarian, character». (Petrina, 1991)

Independently from their individual opinion, historians bear witness to the impact Brazilian architecture provoked in the international panorama, between the middle thirties and the beginning of the sixties.

One of the greatest problems detected in international criticism is the fact that their object is always the work of the same architect — Niemeyer — instead of a wider and representative assemblage of Brazilian architectural works. However, in spite of severe criticism, it is exactly Niemeyer's spectacular architecture that calls attention to Brazil. Reidy and Burle Marx, so very much praised, only win projection after Niemeyer's success.

But, why does São Paulo's architecture is practically ignored in the handbooks? Probably it happens because of its distinct and more sober character, perhaps more similar to the European model that constitutes Zevi, Max Bill and most historians' reference. Probably because neither is it spectacular nor does it cause great impact.

Another question, which is also difficult to understand, is why that architecture, which causes so much sensation after World War II, mysteriously disappears after the end of the sixties.

It probably emerges after World War II because replies to the Modern Movement begin to come out and, under the direction of the CIAMs, there is a search, in different places, for distinct types of production whose proposals can offer new facts, but keep faithful to the fundamentals of the modern canon, and thus make it possible for the movement to survive.

Why it disappears after sixties is difficult to answer. Perhaps — as Lúcio Costa (1979) wants, or rather, as he would like it to be — «because Brazilian architecture no longer exists. There exists the international architecture of English and American magazines». But most probably, after Brasília, the hegemony of an internationally successful kind of architecture — that leaves room for no variations, not even those that do not constitute opposition— is consolidated.

Costa somehow contributed to that. Soon he recognised Niemeyer's capacity to shape plastically, in an innovative and creative way, the specific attributes of a Brazilian culture in perfect consonance with the principles of the modern canon. Full of enthusiasm, he began to build the myth. Following this trail, the real or potential diversity of the movement disappears. Costa (1982) literally states: «The so called Brazilian contemporary architecture movement is, fundamentally, Oscar Niemeyer. The other architects more or less followed what he did».

Costa starts building up a history in which

Niemeyer is the most important, or perhaps, the only protagonist, and almost all historians use it as a source. However, in modern architecture handbooks, they always make laudatory references to Reidy, even if very brief sometimes.

This statement reflects the environment in which there appears a feeling of opposition from the part of the following generation of professionals, who, besides adverse political conditions, will come to face a context in which there is no place for a different type of architecture other than Niemeyer's successful one.

In any way, the Brazilian modern architecture movement seems to come to an end after the construction of Brasilia, or, according to Benévolo, after the 1964 military coup. The only subsequent image is presented by one of the most ferocious critics of Brazilian architecture: Tafuri includes an image of the 1975 Mondadori Editions building in his handbook, probably because it is an Italian example.

As to cultural differences, although canonical texts do not directly mention them, they appear by means of criticism, interpretations and comments, even when they refer to the relationships between produced works and the environment in which they are inserted. The very reference to Brazilian architecture as a manifestation either of a «distant country» or of the «periphery of civilisation» seems to mean something other than geographical distance: the physical distance from the old continent is not as big as the intellectual, theoretical and cultural distances.

In scenery dominated by Europe and the United States, a highly exotic architectural production is labelled according to known theoretical landmarks –neo-classicism, neoexpressionism, surrealism etc. Such classifications tame the production of a wild country, translate it into civilised languages, but, in the process, its original sense, its defects and qualities, its context and references end up getting lost.

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number	subject	assunto	From
1, 2, 3	The covers of three architecture magazines special issues dedicated to modern Brazilian architecture where the theme is the <i>brise-soleil</i> and the climate control mechanisms	Capas de três números especiais de revistas de arquitetura dedicadas à arquitetura moderna brasileira, onde o tema é o <i>brise-soleil</i> e os mecanismos de controle climático.	AA 13/14 sep 1947 AA 42/43 aug 1952 AF nov 1947
4, 5, 6	The Hydro airplane Station by Atilio Correia Lima is an example of Brazilian projects spread out by the pre-canonical documents, which don't appear in the modern architecture handbooks. The Crystal House and the São Paulo Art Museum by Lina Bo Bardi are other examples forgotten by the handbooks.	A Estação de Hidroaviões de Atilio Correia Lima é um exemplo dos projetos brasileiros bastante divulgados nos documentos pré-canônicos que não aparecem nos manuais de arquitetura A Casa de Vidro e o Museu de Arte de São Paulo de Lina Bo Bardi são outros exemplos igualmente esquecidos pelos manuais	Goodwin 1943 Mindlin, 1956 Ferraz, 1933
7, 8	The Pampulha Casino by Oscar Niemeyer and the Modern Art Museum of Rio de Janeiro by Affonso Eduardo Reidy are examples of these two Brazilian modern architecture important personalities work.	O Cassino de Pampulha de Oscar Niemeyer, assim como o Museu de Arte Moderna do Rio de Janeiro são exemplos da obra dessas duas figuras importantes na arquitetura moderna brasileira.	Goodwin 1943 AA 54 may/jun 1954
9, 10	The Maternity Hospital by Rino Levi and the Itápolis House by Gregori Warchavchik are others examples of architecture initially spread out by architecture magazines and later forgotten by modern architecture handbooks.	O Hospital Maternidade de Rino Levi e a Casa Itápolis de Gregori Warchavchik são outros exemplos de arquiteturas inicialmente difundidas e posteriormente esquecidas pelos manuais de arquitetura moderna	AF nov 1947 Sartoris 1931
11, 12, 13, 14	In the same way, the Olinda Water Tower and the Rural School by Luiz Nunes, as the architect house and Landrina Station by João Batista Vilanova Artigas were forgotten too.	Da mesma forma a Caixa d'Água de Olinda e a Escola Rural de Luiz Nunes, assim como a Casa do Arquiteto e a Rodoviária de Landrina de João Batista Vilanova Artigas foram igualmente esquecidas.	AR 567, mar 1944 Mindlin, 1956
15, 16, 17	Three images are spread out in all of modern architecture handbooks: The Education Ministry by Costa, Niemeyer, Reidy, Moreira, Leão, Vasconcelos, the Pampulha Chapel by Niemeyer and the Pedregulho Social Housing Complex.	Três imagens aparecem em todos os manuais de arquitetura moderna: o Ministério da Educação de Costa, Niemeyer, Reidy, Moreira, Leão, Vasconcelos; a Capela de Pampulha de Niemeyer e o Conjunto Pedregulho de Reidy.	AF feb 1943 AA 06 dec 1946 AA 42/43 aug 1952
18	The Brazilian Pavilion at the New York World's fair by Costa and Niemeyer is the first Brazilian project build out of the country.	O Pavilhão de Nova York de Costa e Niemeyer é o primeiro projeto brasileiro construído fora do país.	AA 13/14 sep 1947
19, 20, 21	Three examples of an architectural element which became a characteristic of Brazilian modern architecture, the <i>brise-soleil</i> : The Education Ministry, The Brazilian Association Press and the Brazilian Pavilion at New York World's fair.	Três exemplos de um elemento que se consolidou como característica da arquitetura moderna brasileira: o <i>brise-soleil</i> : Ministério da Educação, Associação Brasileira de Imprensa e o Pavilhão do Brasil na Exposição Interbacional de Nova York	Goodwin 1943
22, 23, 24	Le Corbusier verifies, in an article for L'Architecture d'Aujourd'hui (1947), a new kind of office building created by Brazilian architects (he refers to the high buildings where the climate control mechanisms transcend their function and turn into elements of formal definition) and signs three examples: Education Ministry, Brazilian Association Press and Railroad Station office by Reidy	Le Corbusier constata em um artigo para a revista L'Architecture d'Aujourd'hui de 1947 a existência de um novo tipo de edifício de escritórios criado pelos arquitetos brasileiros (referindo-se obviamente aos edifícios em altura onde os mecanismos de controle solar se convertem em elementos de definição formal) e aponta três exemplos: o Ministério da Educação, a Associação Brasileira de Imprensa e o edifício da Estação Ferroviária de Reidy.	AA 13/14 sep 1947
25, 26, 27	Goodwin insinuates and Hitchcock reaffirms the existence, in the modern Brazilian architecture, of an open architecture, which would characterise the (south and north) American work in the pure wrightian tradition. Rino Levi's houses are good examples of that production.	Goodwin insinua e Hitchcock reafirma a existência na arquitetura moderna brasileira de uma arquitetura aberta que caracterizaria os trabalhos realizados no novo mundo na mais pura tradição wrightiana. As casas de Rino Levi são dois bons exemplos dessa produção.	Mindlin, 1956
28, 29, 30, 31	Brasília is the recurrent theme in the handbooks written after the sixties. Benévolo, Tafuri and Frampton are three of the historians that include this theme in their handbooks. In the examples: The Three Power Square and the Bus Terminal published by Benévolo, the Pilot Plan by Tafuri and the Esplanade of Ministries by Frampton.	Brasília é o tema mais recorrente nos manuais de arquitetura moderna publicados após os anos sessenta: Benévolo, Tafuri e Frampton são três dos historiadores que incluem esse tema em seus manuais. Nos exemplos: a Praça dos Três Poderes e a Rodoviária publicados por Benévolo, o Plano Piloto por Tafuri e a Esplanada dos Ministérios por Frampton.	Benévolo, 1960. Tafuri, 1976. Frampton, 1980
32, 33	As examples of a exaggerated formalism, Max Bill quotes the Canoas House in Rio de Janeiro and the São Paulo Bienal de Plastic Arts building in Ibirapuera	Como exemplos de um formalismo maneirista, Max Bill cita a Casa de Canoas no Rio de Janeiro e o edifício da Bienal de Artes Plásticas de São Paulo no Ibirapuera.	Mindlin, 1956
34	The Modern Art of Caracas' inverted pyramid is an example quoted by Frampton where he identifies the revival of a neoclassical tradition.	A pirâmide invertida do Museu de Arte Moderna de Caracas é um dos exemplos citado por Frampton onde ele identifica a retomada da tradição neoclássica	Mindlin, 1956

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KEYWORDS

Brazilian modern architecture, modern architectural handbooks, modern architecture historiography

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